

FORMATION OF READING AND LISTENING COMPREHENSION COMPETENCE OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the criteria for assessing students' reading literacy. In particular, there are international programs PIRLS (International Reading and Comprehension Survey), which determines the quality, level and level of education in the world, and they are widely used as a criterion for further improving the quality of education in developed countries. referred to.

Key words: quality of education, text, comprehension, analysis, criteria, test, primary education.

It is known that international programs for evaluating student literacy, in particular, PISA, are based on world standards for evaluating the level of reading comprehension of primary school students. Forming the ability to communicate is the main advantage of modern educational methods. The size of the text and its age selection are very important in reading comprehension.

Interesting texts related to nature and the animal world and their reading comprehension also provide interdisciplinary integration. It is known that now English language classes are being held for primary classes as well. Even in schools, among simple texts and simple tasks, the method of listening and understanding takes a leading place.

Through this, the listener pays special attention to the pronunciation and emphasis of words.

In the period of changes, the educational system requires rapid development based on social processes. Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society. Taking this into account, special attention is being paid to strengthening the material and technical base of general education schools and pre-school educational institutions, to creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for the young generation to receive comprehensive education. Also, on the initiative of the President, students who have completed the 9th grade, parents and according to their own wishes, consciously enter the vocational college, academic lyceum or the schools where they were educated, compulsory "Economics and society" No. 3(94) -2 2022 www.iupr.ru 67 establishing that they can continue their education created all kinds of convenience for young people. As a result of such reforms implemented in our country, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, this situation is driving the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists to increase even more. The satisfaction of this demand, in turn, creates the need to increase the interest in reading and classes among young people and to increase the attention of teachers to all-round education through modern social innovations. Experts of the Independent Institute for Monitoring the Formation of Civil Society, taking into account that such requirements are very important for today's education system, some advanced measures

aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of education and science in most foreign countries studied experiments.

In particular, PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), which determines the quality, level and level of education in the world, PIRLS (International Study on Reading and Comprehension of the Text), TIMSS (Mathematics and Science Quality Study at School) There are a number of international programs, such as international monitoring), which are widely used as a criterion for improving the quality of education in developed countries. More than 50 countries are participating in the PIRLS study. The purpose of this international research is to study the readiness of primary school students in reading and receiving texts in countries with different educational systems, as well as the factors in the educational system that cause students to achieve different levels of achievement. consists of identifying and evaluating specific characteristics. Of course, such research is of great importance for workers in the field of public education, scientists, methodologists, teachers, parents and public representatives. TMSS is also widely used in the education system of the world countries. The TMSS program was organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA), and this study examined the quality of education in mathematics and social studies among students in grades 4 and 8, determines the level, attitude to science, interest. It is held once every 4 years. Similar to the PIRLS study, this study will conduct additional surveys of students, school administrators, and teachers to identify key barriers to learning in science. This makes it possible to compare educational standards developed in that country and educational efficiency with other countries. According to the results of TMSS research in 2015, the educational system of countries such as the USA, Singapore, Hong Kong, the Republic of Korea, Japan, Russia, and Great Britain had the highest indicators.

Listening, or listening comprehension, is the first and most important skill that language learners need to master in learning a new language. This is a receptive skill, meaning that newcomers to language learning learn new words from what they hear or listen to. The ability to receive affects the ability to produce. If only they knew how to listen; as a result, they understand effective skills, i.e. speaking and writing, and even have good speech. To be a good listener, students need to think actively while listening. Listening is involved in many language learning processes, both in and out of the language classroom. Improving listening skills is the basis for developing other language skills.

References:

- 1.Бабанский, Ю. О дидактических основах повышения эффективности обучения [Текст]/ Ю. О. Бабанский, М.: Педагогика- 2006.
- 2.Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантиришда интегратив технологиялардан фойдаланиш имкониятлари” С. Шарифзода., Илм сарчашмалари., 9., 102-105. 2021.
- 3.Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантиришда интегратив ёндашувнинг аҳамиятли жиҳатлари” С. Шарифзода., “Ўзбекистонда психология фанларининг истиқболи” Республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари, 2020.
- 4.Пидкасистого П. И.. Педагогика: Учеб. пособие для студ. пед. вузов и пед. колледжей [Текст]/ Под ред. П. И. Пидкасистого. М.: Педагогическое общество России, 2006.

5.Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF GROWING LOGICAL THINKING OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology, 3(5), 33-37.

6.Madrakhimovich, K. E. (2023). Didactic Principles of Developing Logical Thinking in Students. New Scientific Trends and Challenges, 97-100.

